

FUTURAL

Empowering the **FUT**ure through innovative Smart
Solutions for **rURAL** areas

**Rural Innovation Ecosystems in Action — the
FUTURAL case**

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Executive Summary

Rural regions across the EU grapple with complex challenges, frequently described as "wicked problems," which demand systemic and innovative solutions. Issues such as depopulation, inadequate access to essential services, and environmental fragility highlight the need for targeted interventions. Examining FUTURAL's strategy through the lens of Rural Innovation Ecosystems (RIE) underscores the importance of multi-actor approaches and collaborative governance, community-driven innovation, and a focus on transformative outcomes.

This report details the operationalization of RIE principles within FUTURAL, focusing on the Multi-Actor Pilots (MAPs) as localized innovation ecosystems. It analyses the set-up and the structures of the MAPs, highlighting the diversity of their leadership typologies and stakeholders' composition. It also provides insights into the processes of co-creation and of capacity building. Finally, it explores the thematic domains of the project, and the methodologies implemented, showcasing FUTURAL as a replicable model for rural innovation. By integrating diverse stakeholders and employing participatory methodologies, FUTURAL aims to achieve transformative, sustainable, and scalable impacts.

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List of abbreviations

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AIS	Agricultural Innovation System
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge & Innovation System
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
EU-RIF	European Union Rural Innovation Forum
GREMI	Groupe de Recherche Européen sur les Milieux Innovateurs
MAP	Multi-actor Pilots
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
IE	Innovation Ecosystem
SI	Social Innovation
TIM	Territorial Innovation Models
RIE	Rural Innovation Ecosystem

1. Introduction

Rural areas are an integral part of Europe, covering 80% of its territory and housing almost 30% of its population. These regions contribute significantly to Europe's ecological, cultural, and social fabrics. However, they also face persistent and complex challenges that threaten their sustainability and vitality. Issues such as depopulation, aging demographics, economic marginalization, and climate vulnerability characterize many rural areas, particularly those that are geographically remote or socio-economically disadvantaged. Ceseracciu et al., 2023, describe these challenges as “wicked problems” – interconnected, multifaceted issues that defy simple solutions and require systemic, innovative responses.

Innovation has emerged as a critical tool to address these challenges, offering transformative potential to reshape new understandings and practices in rural contexts and create sustainable opportunities for development. Over time, rural innovation policies have evolved in tandem with broader development paradigms, shifting from top-down, exogenous approaches to the more participatory, place-based frameworks of neo-endogenous development (Georgios et al., 2021). Indeed, the more recent neo-endogenous theory, derives from an overcome of the idea of development purely based on endogenous factors such as territorial, human or social capitals, where “local control remains at the heart of neo-endogenous development but the need to embrace ‘extra-local’ factors is also emphasized (Ray 2001).” (Bosworth et al., 2016, p. 428). In this transition, the role of innovation changed considerably to become a process that must be primarily linked to existing social needs and is more probably organizational and/or institutional rather than technological (Bock, 2016; Neumeier, 2011). This shift aligns with the broader understanding of innovation as a process that must respond to specific social and environmental needs, stressing the role of local actors and knowledge systems.

This paradigm shift has been particularly notable in agricultural and rural contexts; in the former, approaches to innovation evolved from linear models where agricultural innovations were “transferred” to farmers-adopters (Klerkx et al., 2012; Röling, Niels, 1990), to the vast literature of Agricultural Innovation Systems (AIS) theory focusing on the complex interactions between a multitude of players (institutions and infrastructures) and sub-systems constituting innovation (Klerkx et al., 2012). This theory has later been integrated into the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) framework, currently used in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). However, rural challenges extend beyond agriculture, necessitating a broader, systemic approach to innovation that encompasses the social, digital, and institutional dimensions. In recent years, the concept of Innovation Ecosystems (IEs) has gained traction as a framework able to understand both the dynamic interactions among actors, resources, and institutions, and the processes of co-evolution and co-creation of value. Granstrand and Holgersson (2020) define IEs as “the evolving set of actors, activities, and artifacts, and the institutions and relations” that shape innovative performances.

While extensively applied in urban and industrial contexts, the IE approach has only recently been explored in rural settings, where unique characteristics such as sparse populations, cultural heritage, and reliance on natural resources demand tailored solutions (European Commission et al., 2024; Scaringella and Radziwon, 2018). The European Union has recognized the potential of rural innovation ecosystems in its Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, which emphasizes building “strong innovation ecosystems that bring together public and private players” to address regional challenges (European Commission, 2021). This focus aligns with the quadruple helix model of innovation, which integrates the four helices represented by government, academia, industry, and civil society to create inclusive, context-sensitive solutions (Carayannis and Campbell, 2009).

The aim of this technical report is to contribute to the development of the concept of RIE in line with the recent efforts and to showcase FUTURAL Horizon project as practical example of RIE. This begins by outlining the theoretical foundations of RIE, encompassing the concepts of Territorial Innovation Models (TIMs), Innovation Ecosystems (IE), and Social Innovation (SI), and explains how these approaches collectively address the complex challenges of rural areas. The report then delves into the Horizon Europe project FUTURAL as a practical application of the RIE concept, illustrating its principles through Multi-Actor Pilots (MAPs) across diverse European contexts. By examining FUTURAL's multi-actor and context approach, iterative and interdependent innovation processes, and transformative ambitions, this report highlights the potential of RIEs to create systemic change in rural governance. The subsequent sections provide an in-depth analysis of FUTURAL's operational framework, thematic domains, and Smart Solutions, offering a comprehensive understanding of how RIE principles can be translated into innovations with transformative ambition.

2. The concept of Rural Innovation Ecosystem

The concept of Rural Innovation Ecosystems (RIE) builds on and integrates three distinct yet complementary theoretical approaches: Territorial Innovation Models (TIMs), Innovation Ecosystems (IE), and Social Innovation (SI). Together, these approaches provide a comprehensive framework for addressing the complexities of rural development by leveraging place-based dynamics, promoting diverse collaborations, and driving transformative change.

2.1 Territorial Innovation Models

Territorial Innovation Models (TIMs) focus on the unique characteristics of a region or locality as a foundation for innovation. They highlight the importance of place-based approaches, where geographic, cultural, and economic specificities are leveraged to advance collective learning and development. TIMs often emphasize localized interactions among key actors — such as businesses, public institutions, and academia — as central to generating innovative outcomes. Historically, TIMs have evolved from early theories that stressed geographic proximity as a prerequisite for innovation. For example, the concept of the "innovative milieu" introduced by the Groupe de Recherche Européen sur les Milieux Innovateurs (GREMI), emphasized how the spatial clustering of actors could enhance knowledge exchange and spur innovation (Camagni, 1995). However, as globalization and digitalization have advanced, TIMs have adapted to recognize that innovation can also result from combining local knowledge with global expertise.

This shift has more recently introduced the idea of "anchoring projects," where local initiatives might interact dynamically with external networks and resources to drive development (Jeannerat and Crevoisier, 2022).

In the context of RIEs, TIMs are particularly relevant to rural areas, where natural resources, cultural heritage, and traditional practices play a critical role in shaping innovation. By integrating TIM principles, RIEs recognize and ensure that rural innovation is grounded in the unique assets and challenges of each region, fostering solutions that are deeply embedded in their local context.

2.2 Innovation Ecosystems

IE extend the TIM framework by emphasizing the dynamic and co-evolutionary nature of innovation. Originating from ecological studies, the concept of ecosystems was adapted to study business ecosystems to describe networks of interdependent actors who collaboratively create value (Moore, 1993). Since then, the concept of IE was developed to tackle the challenges of technological interconnectivity and the evolving characteristics of innovation processes. Indeed, within the extensive body of literature dealing with IE, one branch focuses on its territorial application, and it relates to TIM literature. However, differently from TIMs, which prioritize the geographic dimension, IEs deepens on the relational and systemic aspects of innovation. This includes the interactions among a wide array of stakeholders, such as businesses, government bodies, academia, and civil society. Moreover, IE literature underlines that ecosystems are not static as they evolve over time, with actors adapting to changes in the environment, technologies, and societal needs. Central to this perspective is the concept of co-creation, where value is generated collaboratively rather than in isolation.

In rural contexts, IEs expand the innovation landscape by incorporating diverse actors who may not traditionally be involved in the innovation process. For example, civil society organizations and local communities often play a more prominent role in rural IEs, contributing insights and resources that reflect the specific needs of their regions. By integrating IE principles, RIEs foster

dynamic, multi-actor networks that enable rural areas to co-create and upscale innovative solutions.

2.3 Social Innovation

Social innovation has become a cornerstone of rural development, reflecting the growing recognition that technological advancements alone are insufficient to address the deep-seated social and economic issues faced by rural communities. Neumeier (2011) highlights the role of social innovation initiatives that “are primarily concerned with meeting social needs and improving human well-being, often through collaborative and participatory processes” in fostering collective action and empowering communities to drive change from within. Unlike traditional innovation models that prioritize technological outputs, social innovation emphasizes co-creation processes that respond directly to local needs and aspirations. Indeed, the transformative potential of social innovation is particularly evident in marginal rural areas, where it can address issues such as social exclusion, governance gaps, and the underutilization of resources. The Horizon project SIMRA demonstrated how social innovation can create new opportunities for collaboration and resilience in rural contexts, offering pathways to institutional and cultural change (Kluvankova et al., 2021; Rogelja et al., 2023). Moreover, as Jeannerat and Crevoisier (2022) argue, integrating social innovation into broader innovation ecosystems can create synergies that enhance their transformative capacity.

The SI perspective is particularly relevant to rural areas, where many challenges — such as depopulation, aging populations, and social exclusion — are deeply rooted in social structures. SI approaches prioritize the active involvement of communities in identifying problems and co-developing solutions. This aligns with the neo-endogenous rural development paradigm, which emphasizes local agency and bottom-up approaches while recognizing the importance of external networks and resources (Bosworth et al., 2016).

In the context of RIEs, SI serves as a catalyst for transformative change by addressing systemic issues and fostering new forms of institutional collaboration and innovation. For example, projects that improve access to digital tools in rural areas not only enhance connectivity but might also strengthen community cohesion and participation. By embedding SI principles, RIEs ensure that innovation processes are inclusive and aligned with the broader goals of societal sustainability and resilience.

2.4 RIE: integration of TIMs, IEs and SI

The integration of these three approaches - TIMs, IEs, and SI - enables RIEs to address the multi-dimensional challenges of rural areas comprehensively. TIMs ensure that innovation is rooted in the specificities of place, leveraging local resources and collective learning processes. IEs introduce a systemic, interactive, relational perspective that facilitates collaboration among diverse actors across geographic and organizational boundaries. Finally, SI imbues the RIE framework with a transformative vision, ensuring that innovation not only addresses immediate needs but also contributes to long-term societal change.

This holistic integration is critical in rural areas, where challenges are interconnected, and solutions must balance economic, social, and environmental dimensions. By combining these perspectives, RIEs provide a robust framework for fostering sustainable, inclusive, and transformative innovation in rural contexts.

3. Operationalizing RIE

The application of the RIE principles in the FUTURAL project demonstrates how theoretical concepts can be translated into practical, impactful strategies. By aligning these principles with the methodologies and goals of the FUTURAL project, RIE offers a replicable framework for driving innovation in rural areas. In doing so, FUTURAL exemplifies a systems-based approach to addressing the complex challenges faced by rural communities.

3.1 Multi-actors and contexts

The success of innovation ecosystems lies in their ability to engage diverse stakeholders across sectors, facilitating collaboration and shared value creation. As mentioned, innovation ecosystems thrive on the interplay of actors, activities, and artifacts within a relational network. FUTURAL operationalizes this concept through its Multi-Actor Pilots (MAPs), which bring together public, private, academic, and civil society sectors. This builds upon and enhances the quadruple helix model, incorporating public actors (such as public administrations, economic entities, policymakers, funding agencies, and regional development bodies), private entities (including businesses from primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors, agrifood and rural enterprises, business associations, unions, and innovation intermediaries like clusters or agencies), research and academic institutions (universities, research centres, and independent researchers), and civil society (comprising NGOs and civil society organizations). A key emphasis is placed on the pivotal role of rural civil society in driving the innovation co-creation process within FUTURAL, reinforcing the project's strong foundation in social innovation. In fact, on the one hand, this diverse participation ensures that the complex, varied socio-economic context is considered and represented overall the process. On the other hand, FUTURAL targeted innovations are primarily “community-led”, which means that the collaborative creation of the aimed innovative output should primarily start from the rural community needs. This participatory approach reflects as mentioned the principles of social innovation.

3.2 Eco systemic approach

Rural innovation ecosystems are characterized by their iterative and adaptive methodologies, which allow for continuous alignment with local needs and contexts. Inspired by the Build-Measure-Learn loop of Lean Startup methodology (Blank, 2017; Ries, 2011), FUTURAL employs a phased approach of prototyping, testing, piloting, and demonstrating smart solutions. Each phase is marked by robust feedback loops, enabling stakeholders to refine solutions and re-orient them towards the real needs of the rural contexts, based on real-world inputs and outcomes.

Moreover, this iterative process facilitates the integration of diverse knowledge systems. As described by Crevoisier and Jeannerat (2009), rural innovation requires the interplay of tacit and explicit knowledge — local insights rooted in traditions and practices, combined with global technological expertise. FUTURAL’s community-led innovation process based on structured co-creation and capacity building programs, provide specific platforms (MAPs workshops) for this knowledge exchange, ensuring that solutions are both contextually relevant and technologically robust.

3.3 Transformative ambition

FUTURAL’s ambitions extend beyond the delivery of technological solutions to the systemic transformation of rural governance, societal behaviours, and economic activities. This aligns with the notion of transformative innovation policy, which seeks to address societal challenges through systemic change (Diercks et al., 2019). The transformative potential of innovation ecosystems is further supported by Jeannerat and Crevoisier (2022), who argue for innovation policies that

reshape institutional practices and foster new socio-economic dynamics. FUTURAL exemplifies these ambitions through the work of MAPs, who function as a localized ecosystem addressing specific regional challenges. On the one hand, by co-developing and adopting cutting-edge technologies, MAPs aim to tackle the complex rural wicked issues which have been synthesized in five different macro “domains”. On the other hand, MAPs aim at going beyond the mere introduction of new digital artifacts, by promoting collaborative governance models and encouraging proactive community involvement in decision-making processes, as institutional innovations.

3.4 RIE in FUTURAL

The FUTURAL project translates the theoretical principles of RIE into tangible outcomes through its MAPs. These localized innovation ecosystems serve as experimental hubs for co-creating and implementing solutions that address the specific challenges of rural areas.

3.4.1 Setup and structure of MAPs

A distinctive feature of the MAPs is their intentional diversity, selected to represent the wide-ranging geographical, socio-cultural, and economic characteristics of rural Europe, as well as to showcase varied leadership typologies and stakeholder compositions. This diversity ensures that the solutions developed through FUTURAL are adaptable, inclusive, and reflective of the varied

Figure 1 - Multi Actor Pilots in FUTURAL

realities of rural Europe. Each MAP is uniquely tailored to address the specific challenges and opportunities of its rural setting.

1. Plains and Agricultural Regions (Birda MAP): Birda, Romania, represents a predominantly agricultural area with opportunities in sustainable farming and circular economy practices. However, it faces challenges such as labour mobility, water management issues, and limited local tourism.
2. Mountainous Villages (Durungaldea MAP): Durungaldea, Spain, contrasts industrialized urban areas with sparsely populated natural zones. The MAP focuses on sustainable tourism, rural connectivity, and leveraging the strengths of the Basque Country's economic and environmental diversity.
3. Island Rurality (Kythira MAP): Kythira, Greece, is a sparsely populated island. Its MAP focuses on ecotourism and new learning opportunities on sustainable agriculture. The challenges include youth migration, underexploited natural heritage and the need for sustainable development to balance environmental conservation with tourism growth.
4. Peripheral Rural-Urban Interface (Jonava MAP): Jonava, Lithuania, highlights the dynamics of a rural-urban fringe, with challenges concerning scarce opportunities for young population and the non-trivial equilibrium between natural ecosystems management and local economic activities. The MAP aims at enhancing civic participation by emphasizing e-governance and to monitor and preserve the ecosystem through the development of data-informed bio-diversity score.

5. Mountainous and Alpine Areas (Pongau MAP): Pongau, Austria, combines mountain tourism-driven economic strength with challenges such as climate adaptation and managing the impacts of seasonal industries. Its focus includes bioeconomy innovations to promoting a circular economy and a digital platform to support the design of a smart vacancy management strategy at municipal level.
6. Coastal Areas (Westhoek MAP): Situated in Belgium, Westhoek emphasizes aging population, climate resilience, water resource management, and the integration of natural and agricultural landscapes, leveraging its proximity to coastal and protected regions. This MAP focuses on improving citizens' access to services and addressing climate resilience.

3.4.2 Leadership typologies and stakeholders composition

The diversity of MAPs extends to their leadership structures, reflecting different stakeholder strengths and priorities:

- **Municipal-Led** (Jonava and Birda MAPs) The local government takes the lead in Jonava and Birda, demonstrating how municipalities can drive digital transformation and infrastructural improvements.
- **Province-Led** (Westhoek MAP): The Provincial Authority of West Flanders engages in rural networking, environmental sustainability, and community-driven innovation, focusing on territorial development, water management, environmental protection, and policy development.
- **Regional Institution** (Pongau MAP): The leadership here reflects a coalition of regional authorities in charge of regional planning, local transport, commercial development, and services and advocacy for communities.
- **Regional Associations** (Durangaldea MAPs): The Urkiola Rural Development Association promotes rural development projects in Durangaldea and has significant expertise in rural networking, environmental sustainability and community-led innovation, as well as policy design.
- **Community-Led** (Kythira MAP): The Kytherian Foundation for Culture & Development leads this MAP, representing grassroots-level engagement and focusing on leveraging local cultural and natural assets for innovation.

Each MAP also integrates stakeholders from the quadruple helix framework, including:

- **Public Sector:** Local governments, policymakers, and rural development agencies provide institutional support and facilitate policy alignment.
- **Private Sector:** SMEs, business associations, and innovation intermediaries contribute expertise and resources for the development and scaling of solutions.
- **Academia:** Universities and research institutions offer technical knowledge and analytical capacity, particularly in digital and social innovation.
- **Civil Society:** Community organizations and NGOs ensure that solutions are aligned with local priorities and socio-cultural realities.

3.4.3 Co-creation and capacity building

The Build-Measure-Learn cycle of the Lean Start-up methodology is embodied in two main levels of MAP activities, namely co-creation and capacity building. Regarding the co-creation activity, defined as “active engagement of stakeholders who hold different types of knowledge and resources with the aim to generate collaboratively outcomes (Voorberg et al., 2015; Wilk et al., 2020), this is organized in FUTURAL according to 4 different phases, namely:

1. **Prototyping:** Initial development of early prototypes based on ideas coming from community-identified challenges.
2. **Testing:** Controlled environment trials to gather feedback and assess feasibility.

3. **Piloting:** Live activity, implementation of a preferred product or solution in a selected area or population prior to full rollout.
4. **Demonstration:** Full-scale deployment to showcase impacts and scalability.

Figure 2 - Community-led innovation process in FUTURAL: co-creation and capacity building phases

It is worth to underline how the since the first phase, MAP and SS providers worked together to build an early prototype including the minimum features with the least resources invested possible, the “Minimum Viable Product – MVP”. Next, the loop of testing and feedback involve the rural community with the aim to continuously nurture, monitor and re-orient the development of innovations towards their real needs. In this iterative process, Co-creation Workshops play a critical role.

Each MAP has to organize at least one workshop for each co-creation phase (for a total of 3 across FUTURAL project) and, while for each of these the aim is to engage an increasing number of stakeholders from the local community, their focus evolves with the increasing maturity of the SS co-created. While the first workshops aimed at collecting the minimum features that potential users wanted for their MAPs, the following ones aim at testing and giving feedback back on the versions in controlled and live environments, until the final demonstrations and evaluations.

In parallel, with the aim to foster the interplay between tacit and explicit knowledge, Capacity Building Workshops are organized both at MAPs and more general consortium level. Indeed, while local knowledge from workshop participants provides essential context and ensures cultural relevance, external expertise brought by SS providers introduces cutting-edge technologies and methodologies. In FUTURAL, such combination is ensured through a structured programme with 4 different phases (assess and analyse, design, deliver and assess) and the organisation of 3 Capacity Building Workshops at MAP level and 3 additional ones within the framework of the EU Rural Innovation Forum (EU-RIF) event.

In the first case the workshops focus on the local context of the MAPs, identifying target groups and learning needs of future users, to then developing ad-hoc training modules. In the case of the Capacity Building workshops of the EU-RIF events, the aim is to foster the sharing of learning

paths between the different localised RIEs, to share best practices, potential obstacles and lessons learned.

This integration creates solutions that are both innovative and deeply rooted in local realities, reinforcing the ecosystemic nature of RIEs. This dual focus on development and empowerment ensures that innovations are sustainable and integrated into the local ecosystem.

3.4.4 Smart Solutions and thematic domains

FUTURAL ambition is to introduce innovations with a potential of systemic changes, crucial in order to reach sustainability goals in rural societies across EU. Such non-linear systemic change is the necessary pre-condition that leads to fundamental, qualitative changes in societies' cultures, structures and practices (Loorbach et al., 2017).

To this aim, FUTURAL approach started from a participatory identification of the main social challenges perceived by local stakeholders of MAPs. Some of these challenges are common across the different MAPs, namely:

- Climate crisis effects on rural territories
- Increasing difficulties in preserving and valorising local resources in rural areas
- Scarce economic opportunities
- Youth leaving
- Aging population
- Poor condition of local infrastructures
- Scarce accessibility of local services

Once MAPs locally agreed on their local priorities, FUTURAL consortium proceeded by grouping these challenges under 5 main thematic domains and associating to each of these grouped challenges 8 innovative Smart Solutions.

Figure 3 - 5 Thematic domain of FUTURAL challenges

The 5 thematic domains represent the level of synthesis between localized problems of rural societies and macro paths of systemic changes that the different RIEs across EU pursue to reach sustainability goals.

The concrete outcomes of this transformative innovation process are in fact the Smart Solutions, new digital artifacts introduced in the different RIEs represented by MAPs. In the ecosystem literature artifacts include products and services, tangible and intangible resources, technological and non-technological resources, and other types of system inputs and outputs, including innovations. Within FUTURAL, the co-developed Smart Solutions are the most evident new artifacts that will be introduced in the different rural communities. These digital solutions offer eight different digital service typologies to the community and will be based and accessible mainly through online-platforms. These technological artifacts are added to and will interact with already existing technological and non-resources, natural, physical, human. The table 1 summarizes the relation between MAPs, their challenges, the macro thematic domain and the relative SS under co-creation. The next paragraph discusses the transformative potential of each MAP associated for each thematic domain.

Table 1 - MAPs challenges, thematic domains and smart solutions

	Challenge 1	Thematic domain & Smart Solution 1	Challenge 2	Thematic domain & Smart Solution 2
BIRDA	<p>Continuous flooding events in local rural area of Barzava river.</p>	<p>Climate adaptation and mitigation</p> <p>Online platform delivering open courses to improve social knowledge of water challenges.</p>		
DURANGALDEA	<p>Transport systems vulnerable to natural disasters.</p>	<p>Resilience to shocks</p> <p>Online platform to monitor vital infrastructure, travel time to infrastructure or services (e.g., hospitals), hard-to-reach areas (e.g., firefighter access), and general accessibility.</p>		
JONAVA	<p>Damage to local agricultural production due to</p>	<p>Biodiversity and Ecosystem management</p>	<p>Ageing population and lack of opportunities:</p>	<p>Citizen engagement and quality of life</p>

	native free-ranging bison population.	<p>Online eGovernment platform to facilitate communication channels between stakeholders and citizens to engage rural citizens in co-creating practices and policies.</p>		
KYTHIRA¹	Youth leaving island, locals lack education, skills development and training to broaden their interests and acquire modern skills.	<p>Citizen engagement and quality of life</p> <p>Online platform to directly involve local citizens and tourists in the management of local hiking trails.</p>		
PONGAU	Agrifood system inefficiencies due to poor diversification of local bio-derived	<p>Circular economy, Biodiversity and Ecosystem management</p>	<p>Inefficient use of space. Majority of infrastructure (hotels, lifts, spa)</p>	<p>Resilience to shocks</p>

¹ Differently from the original plan of the project, an additional SS will be co-created in Kythira island to deal with the poor state of some local infrastructures. A crowdsensing platform will be co-developed with the aim to assess bridges based on rural traffic trends to help estimate the risk likelihood and severity of infrastructure problems to anticipate preventive measures. This SS refers to the Resilience to shocks domain.

products and production of **waste**; **High dependence on tourism**: Businesses and villages still mainly rely on winter (skiing) and summer tourists (hiking, cycling).

Online circular bioeconomy platform will provide knowledge on resource availability and sharing, product diversification, and employment creation, reducing dependence on tourism.

are used only during high tourist season. Due to underuse, this infrastructure requires regular maintenance. Moreover, old imperial buildings are deteriorating and cannot be used. Renovations are required to make them attractive to investors.

A crowd-sensing platform tool will report data on the state of use of existing infrastructures, especially after a long period of disuse (old buildings, lifts, snow cannons), and will support the participatory definition of an integrated vacancy maintenance plan.

WESTHOEK

Ageing population and distance to social and health infrastructure hinder **access to social and health services**

Citizen engagement and quality of life

Online platform to monitor vital infrastructure, **travel time to infrastructure** or services (e.g., hospitals), hard-to-reach areas (e.g., firefighter access), and **general accessibility**.

Water (quality, shortage). Long periods of drought, low water levels, flooding during heavy rainfall, poor water quality due to erosion, salinisation, pesticides, phosphate and nitrogen observed on water quality observed in the Handzame valley.

Climate adaptation and mitigation

An online platform will be designed to deliver results of a coupled groundwater and surface water model for the Handzame valley sub-basin and support the implementation of flood and drought adaptation strategies under climate change.

Digital Governance in Jonava and Kythira MAP

Digital governance platforms facilitate the interaction and participation of local citizens concerning the public decisions that impact their everyday life. Concerning MAPs, Jonava's e-governance platform enhances civic engagement by allowing citizens to report issues, track municipal services, and provide feedback. This aligns with broader trends in digital transformation, where participatory platforms are reshaping governance structures (Autio, 2017). The anticipated impacts include improved service delivery and increased trust in local government. In Kythira MAP, the online platform promotes eco-tourism and cultural heritage aiming to diversify local economies while preserving traditions. The realisation that participation to local governance is not only easier – thanks to digital means – but also more effective and transparent might strengthen the sense of belonging of citizens in rural areas and, conversely, counteract the sense of abandonment and frustration common in some marginalised areas of Europe. Moreover, whether implemented, such e-government/maintenance platforms might make easier for municipalities or other public institutions to visualize, monitor and get inputs and feedback on their works.

Climate Resilience Tools in Birda and Westhoek MAPs

Hydrological models developed in these regions integrate Nature-Based Solutions with data-driven decision-making. In this sense, digital solutions allow decision makers and practitioners to make use of real-time data to visualize, monitor and take preventive measures regarding water management. In Birda case, the model is expected to provide decision makers with images of surface water management in the context of climate change, future climate change scenarios will be performed, and a set of spatially distributed Nature-Based Solutions will be proposed to reduce the effects of climate change. In Westhoek MAP, the hydrological model will be designed to deliver results of a coupled groundwater and surface water model for the Handzame valley sub-basin and it will focus on supporting the implementation of flood and drought adaptation strategies under climate change. In both cases, the introduced digital artifacts, whether continuously adopted and implemented by local institutions, could bring about systemic changes in the tools and strategies with which local governance adapts to and mitigates the effects of the climate crisis on rural areas. First and foremost, the ability to implement data-informed and nature-based preventive measures. In addition, the information base collected could improve the information and awareness-raising actions of the entire community on the nexus between climate crisis and rural fragility.

Circular economy, Biodiversity and Ecosystem management in Pongau and Jonava MAP

Within this domain the digital platforms permit a more transparent and efficient circulation of information regarding the use of local resources and preservation of natural ecosystem and biodiversity. In Pongau MAP, the online platform will collect and analyse data on specific residue streams, such as sewage sludge from regional wastewater treatment plants and food waste from tourism. On the base of these information, local institutions will be able to propose alternative valorisation pathways of existing regional resources, thus allowing local interested stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding resource utilisation. If institutionally adopted and implemented, the platform can directly show how the presented alternatives can positively impact the region, contributing to its economic, environmental, and social sustainability. Concerning Jonava MAP, the platform will host a set of directly collected and crowd-sourced data and analyses that will allow a) future users to visualise and monitor potential damage due to the passage of free-ranging bisons; b) local authorities to have more information to monitor and preserve the state of local biodiversity (Biodiversity score) . On the one hand, the platform enables greater participation by local actors in the monitoring activity, giving them the opportunity to report any directly observed damage. On the other hand, it increases transparency on the general status of potential damages and the strategies and operational solutions that local institutions implement to limit them. In general, the introduction of this digital solution can support the implementation of

strategies for the coexistence of all actors in the local natural ecosystem and the conservation of its biodiversity.

Improving smart resilience in Pongau, Durangaldea and Kythira MAP

Online crowd-sensing platforms co-developed in this domain aim at supporting the monitoring and visualising the structural health and capability of bridges, road networks and buildings. In case of public infrastructures, an early warning system to detect when normal health values are exceeded will be supplemented. In Durangaldea and Kythira MAP, the SS will allow reporting and monitoring of problematic issues regarding the local rural mobility, which will be all reported over the platform with the tracks status updates, timestamps, and actions taken for issue resolution. The platform will be endowed with an infrastructure monitoring page that will display health status, risk levels, and travel suggestions of the infrastructure monitored. This functionality will work as an early warning system and will help the administrations in charge of infrastructure maintenance key data and information that would considerably improve the decision making before encountering the problem before their actual occurrence. In addition, the platform will be equipped with a page for announcements, so that the same authorities can post relevant announcements and end users can stay informed about updates and important information. Concerning Pongau MAP, the collection and analysis of data on the current use of buildings and spaces in the urban areas of the region will support local institutions to participatively design an integrated vacancy management plan for the 25 municipalities of Pongau. More in details, the platform will host an open and inclusive process of participatory mapping of current vacancies (supply) and potential uses from the different stakeholders of the municipalities such as landlords, real estate agents and developers, local businesses and associations, start-ups etc. (demand).

In both cases, the digital solutions could facilitate participation and active involvement of all the RIE stakeholders in the participatory planning and maintenance of local structures (infrastructures and civil buildings), thus supporting the overall participation of community to local decision making. Together with an improved transparency and thus accountability for the decision-making process, these changes might lead to a better and more effective rapprochement and communication of citizens with the local governance system.

Delivering new competences in Birda and Kythira MAP

Both in Birda and Kythira MAP, localized RIEs focus on co-creating online e-learning platforms with open courses accessible from local rural communities. The learning modules object of these open courses have been designed on the base of the needs and interests of the local community and created with inputs received from local experts, to ensure the material is practical and suited to the contexts. In the case of Birda, given the centrality of the nexus between farming activities and water management for a sustainable local development, the course contents will deal with precision agriculture tools for sustainable farming and advanced techniques in water management. For what concerns Kythira, the courses will focus on local and traditional farming activities such as beekeeping, olive oil production, and herb farming, with the aim of equipping residents — particularly young people — with relevant skills tied to digitalization and innovation.

The platform will be built starting from an existing digital infrastructure, which ensures cross-platform compatibility and supports learning management and course authoring applications. Users will be able access instructional videos, self-assessment quizzes, and progress-tracking features, all of which foster interactive, engaging learning experiences.

The transformative ambition of this innovations is mainly linked to supporting a sustainable and place-based development through the acquisition of new but context-relevant knowledge and competences. To increase the systemic scope of the change, the e-learning platforms targets mainly young people, a fragile part of the society who currently leave rural areas to search opportunities not available in native contexts. That said, the openly accessible courses represent

a viable opportunity to pursue a lifelong education path for both more traditional (elderly people) or new (returning or new residents) segments of the modern rural societies.

4. Conclusions

The FUTURAL project exemplifies the transformative potential of RIE in addressing the complex, interconnected challenges faced by rural areas across Europe. By operationalizing the theoretical principles of RIE, FUTURAL can demonstrate how inclusive, adaptive, and systemic approaches can foster sustainable development in diverse rural contexts.

Key Insights from FUTURAL

1. Multi-Actors and context

FUTURAL highlights the critical importance of engaging diverse stakeholders from the public, private, academic, and civil society sectors. The application of the quadruple helix model ensures that all actors contribute their unique perspectives and resources, resulting in solutions that are not only innovative but also deeply attuned to local needs. The strong emphasis on community co-creation underscores the central role of rural populations as active agents of change, rather than passive beneficiaries.

2. Dynamic Ecosystem Processes

The project's iterative methodology, inspired by the Lean Startup model, enables the continuous refinement of solutions through feedback loops and stakeholder engagement. This adaptive approach ensures that innovations remain relevant and effective in addressing the evolving challenges of rural communities. The integration of tacit (local) and explicit (technical) knowledge is particularly significant, as it bridges the gap between global expertise and local realities.

3. Transformative Ambitions

FUTURAL's focus on systemic impacts demonstrates the potential of RIEs to drive long-term, sustainable change. By addressing issues such as digital exclusion, climate resilience, and economic diversification, the project lays the groundwork for shifts in governance, societal behaviours, and economic structures. The project's emphasis on aligning innovations with global sustainability goals further highlights its commitment to transformative change.

Strategic Implications

The outcomes of FUTURAL can offer valuable lessons for future rural innovation initiatives:

- **Designing for Inclusivity:** Embedding RIE principles from the outset ensures that innovation processes are participatory, equitable, and responsive to local contexts.
- **Scaling Success:** The MAP framework provides a replicable model for scaling rural innovations across different regions, emphasizing the adaptability of ecosystem-based approaches.
- **Policy Alignment:** Aligning project outcomes with EU policies on rural development, digitalization, and sustainability enhances the potential for long-term impact and funding support.

Future Directions

While FUTURAL has achieved significant progress, there remains a need for ongoing research and experimentation to fully realize the potential of RIEs:

- **Evaluating Long-Term Impacts:** Assessing the systemic and transformative effects of the innovations introduced by FUTURAL will provide critical insights into their sustainability and scalability.
- **Refining Methodologies:** Further refining the methodologies used in MAPs, particularly in terms of multi-actor approaches and their value-added in terms of knowledge integration and stakeholder engagement, can enhance the effectiveness of future projects.
- **Multi-actor platforms sustainability:** Exploring strategies and operative solutions to ensure that MAPs and similar multi-actor platforms can continue their work having a role in localised RIEs

Final Reflections

FUTURAL has provided a powerful demonstration of how the theoretical frameworks underpinning RIEs can be translated into practical, impactful solutions. By fostering collaboration, leveraging diverse knowledge systems, and pursuing systemic impacts, the project has set a benchmark for rural innovation. Its successes underline the importance of ecosystem thinking in addressing the complex challenges of rural areas and offer a roadmap for future initiatives seeking to empower rural communities through innovation.

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